

The essence and functions of the concept of development of students' musical thinking

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Annotation: This article discusses the methods and tools of pedagogical forms of formation and development of musical thinking in young students. The essence, tasks and importance of the concept of developing musical thinking will be revealed during the educational process. As a result of pedagogic observations, some recommendations were given regarding the organization of students' independent thinking.

Keywords: lifelong education, thinking, personality, teacher, spirituality, factor, education, upbringing, system, formation, necessity, independent learning, observation, skill, mental education, musical ability, skill, physiologist, psychologist, musicologist, attention.

It depends on how the education system is conducted to make our perfect generation a mature and perfect person in all respects. That is why it is not for nothing that our thinkers say that education is the main tool in the formation of a person. In turn, it is correct to say that this depends on processes such as knowledge-qualification literacy, culture, spiritual and moral norms of the learner, so the issue of achieving a positive formation of the human personality in all aspects has been a unique task of each era. For this reason, the creation of an excellent system of personnel training based on the rich intellectual heritage of the nation, universal values, and the achievements of modern culture, economics, science and technology, is reflected in the Law on Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan and in the legal

regulations of the last five years. In order to improve the development of society, it is necessary to carry out the effective work of pedagogues and students who can think creatively about every issue in order to establish a consistent and meaningful work aimed at training highly creative, capable, highly cultured, talented students with creative qualities.

For this purpose, students are prepared on the basis of world-class achievements in the analysis of musical and creative thinking and the continuous education system, and have a high general and general professional culture, creative and social activity, choose the right way to work independently in the socio-political environment, and have a high level of knowledge. one of the most important tasks is to form a new generation of personnel capable of promoting and solving future tasks. In the implementation of fixed-step activities aimed at general and professional training of talented students, first of all, high school students should be given wide opportunities to show and develop their abilities in relevant fields of knowledge and specific directions of science, to realize their unique talents. .

It is necessary to train a person to acquire knowledge by turning him into a scholar, that is, a creative thinker.

Today, our republic's art, science, production process, the attitude of our citizens to work, raising the standard of living of the population and growing the state require intelligent, creative thinking specialists who embody the above qualities.

For this, there is a need to quickly identify young people with high creative thinking skills and regularly engage with them.

The formation of these processes, the creation of modern pedagogical technologies, and the study of their pedagogical psychological foundations are the requirements of today. For this, of course, the level of the people's demand of the time: the aesthetic education, which adds to the treasure of values, consists in

educating specialists who have musical knowledge based on tools. To fulfill this task, it is necessary to revise the system of training highly educated, cultured and knowledgeable specialists. In this place, specialists with comprehensive musical thinking and broad creative thinking are needed. At this point, it is necessary for future music teachers to have sufficient knowledge and high morale. This is very important for the development of society.

This process is carried out on the following basis:

1. Creating a discussion process in mastering the lesson.
2. Discuss the material in small groups within a polylogue group (class).
3. Creating interest in learning the material by implementing creative thinking based on control and evaluation.

When working as a team, you should pay attention to the following:

- Taking into account the creation of a controversial process in the preparation of lesson material.
- To ensure the emergence of creative thinking based on the goal, to expand musical thinking.
- To create the feature that every student can respect the opinion of others when mastering the material.

It should be taken into account that if students are not ready to analyze theoretical material in the nature of a problem, develop new ideas and fully solve practical problems based on creative thinking, then they will have to find a simple solution. Such skills are gradually formed on a historical basis. Creating students' creative thinking on a group basis is carried out more on the basis of discussion, and it is possible to effectively use the processes of organizing creative thinking, testing knowledge, identifying interests, and directing creativity on a group basis.

Based on the requirements for solving the problem, it can be seen that there are tasks such as the following to determine the solution to this problem:

1. To increase the psychological-pedagogical preparation of students in mastering each lesson material.
2. To determine the ways of directing students' attention to creative thinking and to create the scientific-pedagogical basis of their correct use.
3. Improvement of students' creative thinking skills and so on.

Our observations show that 63% of students do not engage in creative thinking (on a separate systematic basis) only by memorizing the lesson material, but only in the process of strengthening the lesson material. 83% of students are not ready for creative thinking based on the study.

When the students' lecture texts were checked, it was found that the materials aimed at guiding their thinking and strengthening their knowledge on this basis did not exceed 3-7% (it was taken as a basis that the creation of creative thinking was taken into account only in the part of strengthening the lecture texts).

A creative looking professional is beneficial for society, and for this, it is necessary to train the future professional to develop his musical thinking from the time he is a student. It should be explained to the students why and for what purpose this process is necessary.

In order for students to develop their musical thinking and actively study the studied material, it is appropriate to organize their activities on the following basis:

1. In the introductory part of the lesson, special materials are given for observation in order to create creative ideas of students during this lesson.
2. Special questions will be included in the main part of the lesson.
3. It is not recommended to dwell on special questions, and creative ideas are given by the teacher to special questions, if the students cannot find the answer, the

teacher immediately asks guiding questions. If the answer is not found, the teacher will answer it himself, and it will be said based on what considerations the answer was found.

4. After giving the materials, questions or questionnaires will be given based on the lesson material.

To implement the above, we used the following methods and set the following tasks.

- Slight complicating the studied lesson material;
- To increase the attention of students in some of the necessary places of the educational material, and also to introduce materials according to the order;
- Using the questionnaire method to show the student's creative musical thinking;
- Arranging a debate based on who understood the given key phrases and how;
- Carrying out the process of exchange of ideas based on the final result;
- Various extracurricular activities, quizzes, games, etc.

On the basis of the indicated processes, it is appropriate to organize training sessions for students on the following basis:

1. Understanding the lesson material, regularly dealing with students who are beginning to learn well (it is necessary to work with them regularly as much as possible individually);
2. Inquisitive, creative, innovative students (they should not be left to their own devices as "mental" students, on the contrary, it is necessary to encourage them, even with words, to make them more interested in science) it is appropriate to conduct special classes with them.

3. Consistently conduct explanatory work by connecting more lesson materials with information based on science sources with students who try to master the lesson materials and think creatively.
4. There are those who do not understand the lesson materials. It is up to the teacher to work with them. Because the teacher's working time is not infinite, there is a certain limit to the possibilities. In this case, it is necessary to rely only on the pedagogical activity of the teacher. On the basis of a systematic approach to the teaching of the music textbook, it is necessary to re-develop the methodological recommendations used for the development of the students of the artistic works given for teaching music in grades 4-9. Independent works, exercises, visual exercises, written work, extracurricular activities, activities and similar specific activities should be carried out according to a specific program.

In the implementation of the above, we recommend to do the following in order to create students' creativity:

- Organize meaningful debates.
 - Reading problematic essays, conducting written creative works, organizing classes based on various games, conducting activities using stands, using more opportunities of students in organizing educational activities, organizing many activities with the help of computers (developing their musical thinking), organizing distance studies, pedagogical technologies to start more effective teaching methods using the Case method, to organize demonstration classes, to organize conversations about aesthetic culture, to organize seminar classes. From a pedagogical point of view, it is necessary to pay attention to the existence of conflicts that arise

in the development of students' musical thinking. With an individual approach to each student, the following should also be taken into account:

- Non-uniformity of students' knowledge.
- Diversity of students' curiosity.
- Diversity of students' character
- Different shyness of students.
- Students' various mastering of the lesson material, etc.

The issue of training mature personnel is a complex issue, and it is impossible to achieve great success in the future without sharply developing the professional knowledge skills of the young generation. For this, one of the major tasks before the students requires a fundamental change in their attitude towards: social-political, cultural-educational spheres.

In our work today, it is shown the need to convey the experiences of foreign countries, our own national characteristics, cultural and educational wealth to students based on our material and spiritual capabilities. It depends on the extent to which we develop students' independent and creative thinking.

If we do not systematically work with students on the development of their scientific creativity, it will be natural for them to be slow in the learning process, insufficient development of thinking ability, inability to clearly express their opinion, not feeling the need to acquire this or that knowledge.

The task of the teacher is to cultivate positive feelings in students, to form the ideal of developed musical thinking, to be able to see the beauty in life and to create it.

Seeking to clarify the goals of musical education allows us to distinguish the following three pedagogical tasks:

1. Forming emotional things;

2. Consciously form them;

3. To have an active conscious attitude to the art of music.

These three tasks are carried out based on the perception of the art of music and define the following tasks:

The first pedagogical task is to form an emotional (emotional) attitude towards the student based on the perception of a piece of music. Therefore, the sensitivity of the emotional approach to the figurative aspect of music, the active desire to acquire knowledge and skills, the desire to listen and play music, and the awakening of music lessons it is necessary to develop an interest in the warmth of the connection between life.

The second pedagogical task is to create the experience of consciously perceiving the art of music, to be able to receive musical knowledge, to understand the character of musical images without feeling the logic of their development, at the same time to understand them, to come closer to the realization that the ideological basis of the work, its content is life is important. To fulfill this task, it is related to the formation of artistic thinking of students and the ability to independently apply knowledge in new situations. Both of these tasks are performed together. A conscious attitude to music is formed on the basis of the experience of emotional, figurative perception of it.

The third pedagogical task - the process of playing a piece of music on a musical instrument, performing it as a choir is the most convenient form of musicality. It is desirable to form an active-practical attitude to the art of music in students through this tool. In order to solve this task, the formation of the musical culture of our students is supposed to be expressed in such a way that it is related to the process of perception of musical art in students and the development of their musical aesthetic imagination and performance skills. It is important to choose an

artistic image in order to make students feel that they are involved in the process of musical creation from both sides. This aspect of the educational process is closely related to the students and is carried out interrelated with the previous tasks. The goal of music lessons is realized step-by-step, based on the connection between the art of music and life. These relationships are demonstrated by comparing:

a) The expression of the emotional and moral attitude to reality in music and the unique experience of students;

The objective elements of the educational criteria, the experience of music embodied in the emotional and moral attitude of a person to reality and the generalized knowledge through the art of music, the elements that reflect the process of their mastery (musical skills and skills) and the connection of the art of music with life, the laws of music science and thus at the same time, the process of mastering the content of education: it also reflects the formation of moral qualities of a person through genres such as music, dance, lapar. In this regard, the general didactic principles of music lessons indicate the specificity of certain educational stages in connection with life.

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